

Partially Leucistic Indian Sarus Crane in Kheda District, Gujarat

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A partially leucistic Sarus Crane in a pair at a wetland in Kheda district

The Sarus Crane is easily identified as a large, mostly grey bodied crane with pink to reddish legs standing up to 175 cm and a red head (Meine & Archibald 1996). The adults have a naked scarlet head and upper neck, with an ashy-grey crown. The bill is characteristically large and greenish-grey in colour. In flight, the black

primary feathers are distinct against the grey contour feathers. Immatures (juveniles) have a rusty-buff colouring on the head and neck, and the upper parts are marked with brown. Older immatures (subadults) have a dull red head and upper neck and are brownish-grey all over.

Sarus Crane is the tallest flying bird in the world and its normal plumage colour is predominantly grey with no white on dorsal body portion

The Sarus Crane has suffered a rapid population decline, which is projected to continue, as a result of widespread reductions in the extent and quality of its habitat, diversion of habitat for development purposes and linear infrastructures. The Birdlife International "Red Data Book" has placed the Sarus Crane in the 'Vulnerable' category, (not Critically

Endangered or Endangered but is facing high risk of extinction in the wild in the medium-term future) under criteria A1c, d, e; and A2c, d, e. by Birdlife International (2001) and in Appendix-II under CITES, restricting species in trade and Schedule I of Wildlife (Protection) Amendment Act, 2022 in India.

On 14 May 2021, while monitoring Sarus congregation at Bherai wetland, we observed an abnormal coloured Sarus Crane in the wetland. We took photographs of the abnormally coloured individual. The adult individual did not have normal plumage colour. Rather, it had whitish wings, whitish back portion of the body and whitish part of the upper neck. The normal plumaged adult Sarus Crane would have grey wings and body, which indicated that the Sarus which we saw and which had whitish in wings and back portion and part of upper neck was partially leucistic. It may also be noted that a normal adult Sarus Crane has a bare red head and part of the upper neck, a greyish crown, and a long, greenish-grey, pointed bill.

UPL Ltd., through its Sarus Conservation project has been doing a monitoring of Sarus Crane since 2015 along with voluntary participation of farmers and village youth the "Rural Sarus Protection Group". On 12 May 2023, while monitoring congregation of Sarus Cranes in Bherai wetland,

Kheda district, we observed a Sarus pair, in which, one adult bird had plumage characteristics clearly indicating partial leucism. In our opinion, it was the same individual that was seen by us at Bherai wetland on 14 May 2021. The pair was accompanied by two sub-adults too.

Leucism, one of the commonest variety of colour aberration in birds, can be defined as a condition which is related with the partial or total lack of the melanin pigments from the feathers. Grouw (2006) observed a phenomenon which can vary from a few white feathers (partially leucistic) to totally white individuals (completely leucistic). Leucistic birds are more noticeable than the normal coloured counterparts; there is a bigger risk of predation. Moreover, it is also reported that these colour aberrant individuals, in occasional cases, may not be recognised or accepted by its potential mating partner (Mayntz, 2020).

Leucism is well documented in birds in India including Gujarat State. A leucistic Shikra (*Accipiter badius*)

was recently recorded in Pavagarh, Gujarat and it was the first ever record from Gujarat for that species. Our report speaks about the first ever observation record of leucistic Sarus

Crane in Kheda district, Gujarat. In our opinion, it is a very rare phenomenon . We believe that it constitutes the first record in India of existence of partially leucistic Sarus Crane.

Glimpses of a partially leucistic adult Sarus Crane occurring along with other normal plumaged Sarus Cranes in Kheda district, Gujarat State

References

Grouw, H.V. (2006). Not every white bird is an albino: sense and nonsense about colour aberrations in birds. *Dutch Birding* 28: 79–89.

Mayntz, M. (2020). Bird Leucism: About Leucistic Birds and Abnormal Plumages. In: *The Spruce Website* link: <https://www.thespruce.com>. Accessed on 22 May 2021.